

FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF ALPORT SYNDROME IN CHILDREN

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Relevance: It has been established that in the last decade the incidence of Alport syndrome among children has increased, the disease has become more frequently diagnosed. Alport syndrome is a hereditary disease that affects the kidneys, hearing and vision organs. It is rare, but can lead to chronic renal failure and complete hearing loss in childhood. At the same time, timely diagnosis plays a major role in preventing early severe consequences.

In pediatric practice, a thorough study of this pathology allows for timely diagnosis and timely observation even before the onset of severe complications, since early detection improves the patient's condition.

Key words: Alport syndrome, collagen type IV, hereditary nephritis, hematuria, chronic renal failure, hearing loss, genetics.

The main cause of Alport syndrome is mutations in the COL4A3, COL4A4 or COL4A5 genes, which encode type IV collagen chains. This collagen is an important component of the basement membrane of the kidneys, inner ear and eyes. Due to the mutation, the collagen structure is disrupted, and the basement membrane becomes weak. This leads to damage to the glomeruli of the kidneys, hematuria and later proteinuria develop, the structure of the cochlea in the inner ear is disrupted, which leads to hearing loss, as well as changes in the lens and retina of the eyes. Eye symptoms such as anterior lenticonus appear. The first manifestation of the disease is often microhematuria - the presence of red blood cells in the urine, more often during a laboratory examination of urine. With age, proteinuria and signs of impaired renal function appear.

Early diagnostics is often based on the detection of various stigmas of dysembryogenesis in children (gothic palate, syndactyly, aplasia, renal hypoplasia, single kidney). The diagnosis is based on examination, genetic tests, clinical course, urine tests, the presence of hematuria, proteinuria, biochemical blood tests, which show an increase in creatinine, an increase in urea, and a decrease in filtration. Audiometry is used to detect hearing loss in a small patient, and an ophthalmological examination (eye changes) and kidney biopsy (basement membrane changes) are also required. But the most important analysis is genetic testing, the most accurate method for detecting mutations in the type IV collagen genes (COL4A3, COL4A4, COL4A5).

There is currently no specific treatment for Alport syndrome. However, measures are taken to slow the progression of the disease:

- ACE inhibitors and angiotensin II receptor blockers - to reduce pressure in the kidneys and reduce protein in the urine;

- A diet with reduced salt and protein content (table No. 7 according to Pevzner);
- Regular monitoring by a nephrologist, ENT doctor and ophthalmologist;
- Hemodialysis and kidney transplantation in the event of renal failure;
- If necessary - hearing aids.

Conclusion: Alport syndrome is a hereditary pathology that affects the kidneys, hearing and vision, and diagnostics play a major role. Thanks to modern diagnostic methods, especially genetic ones, early detection of the disease has become possible. Although there is no complete cure, proper monitoring and treatment can slow the development of renal failure and improve the quality of life of patients.

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(Подробно о диагностике и наблюдении детей с наследственными нефропатиями, включая синдром Альпорта)

